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SAINT GRIGOL PERADZE
2ND INTERNATIONAL

SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE

DEDICATED TO THE

**900TH ANNIVERSARY OF THE
BATTLE OF DIDGORI**

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ACTIVITIES OF CATHOLIC MISSIONARIES IN THE GEORGIAN LANDS: DIPLOMATIC RELATIONS OR THE POLICY OF CATHOLICIZATION BY EUROPEAN KINGS

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The spread of Catholicism among Eastern Christians had always been a priority of the Papacy. Missionaries sent as diplomatic ambassadors attempted to subdue Eastern Christians to the Papacy, propagating Catholicism, and in turn received strong support from European Kings. The main purpose of the study is to examine the activities of missionaries who came to the Georgian lands and to study the reasons why Catholicism could not spread in the territories.

Georgian ruler had long maintained contact with European rulers, including the Papacy. There was an exchange of letters between Queen Rusudan (1223–1245) and Honorius III and his successor Gregory IX. These relations resulted in the settlement of Franciscan and Dominican missionaries in Georgia between the thirteenth and sixteenth centuries (Flannery 2013: 198). In the 15th century, the Papacy seeking allies against the Ottoman Empire concentrated all its attention on the east. In 1458 the Pope Pius II, hearing of Uzun Hasan Aq Qoyunlu's marriage to the daughter of the Emperor of Trebizond and the alliance the latter had made with the Emperor against the Ottoman Turks, sent Ludovico of Bologna of the Franciscan order to meet Uzun Hasan in Diyarbakir (Piemontese 1991: 194). In December 1460, the monk Ludovico da Bologna returned to the Papal palace with ambassadors from Trebizond, Georgia, and Aq Qoyunlu. Before meeting the Pope, they met with Holy Roman Emperor Frederick III. Looking at Anthony Brier's article, it is clear that the Pope has received the ambassadors with great interest. He also writes that the ambassadors were sent to France and Burgundy by Pope Pius II with a letter, and all expenses were paid (Piemontese 1991: 195).

Beginning in the late 16th century, during the reign of Shah Abbas I, relations with Europe were expanded (Münşi İsgəndər bəy 2009: 34). It is clear from the *Chronicle of Carmelites* that members of the great missionary orders began to flock to the Safavid palace as ambassadors, and also returned as ambassadors of the Safavids, delivering letters of the Safavid Shahs (Chick & Matthee 2012: 160). However, these documents were often distorted and handed over to the other side at the request of the ambassadors. For example, in 1601, Anthony Shirley met with Pope Clement VIII and submitted a document called *Instructions* on behalf of the Shah. The following part of the document deserves particular attention: "Georgians, Armenians and other Christians under his rule also assume your authority". Another document is a letter from Anthony Shirley to Cardinal Chintius Aldobrandini, the Pope's envoy in Prague, as well as concessions of the Shah to Christian merchants, including the so-called "Privilege" (Chick & Matthee 2012:178). However, the document called *Privilege* has caused controversy in historiography. It is doubtful that the document does not present a copy written in Farsi. On the other hand, the language styles of this 18-page document are comparable to other Safavid documents, and it is believed that paragraphs were added by Anthony Shirley. One of the items of *Privilege* which causes controversy in historiography is as follows: "Send preachers and priests to his land. To further strengthen this union, the Shah orders all Christian subjects from all his lands to accept the Universal Church". The sixteenth item, that is, how the question of the unification of Churches was far removed from the syllabus of Shah Abbas I, is clear evidence that Anthony Shirley wrote the document himself. Shah Abbas I would have never agreed to the creation of such "fifth column" (Chick & Matthee 2012: 182).

The Augustinian missionaries, who were considered spies of the Spanish and Portuguese Kings, were especially active in spreading Catholicism in the Georgian lands. In 1614, the report of the priest

Belchior to the Spanish King says that the Georgian Patriarch had granted him the right to live in Georgia. It should be noted that the source confirming the connection of the Georgians with the Augustinian missionaries is the work *Relação Verdadeira*, written by the priest Ambrosio dos Anjos and have currently stored in the national archives of Portugal.

The Augustinians, who won the battle with the Carmelites over the relics of the Queen Ketevan, received permission from the Georgian King to build a residence in Tbilisi (Georgia). This is evidenced by a letter from Teimuraz I to the Pope Urban VIII: "It has been a year since Father Ambrosio of the Augustinian order brought back the dried bones, the remains of my mother from Isfahan, the palace of the Parthian Kingdom. We provided him a land to build a residence in exchange for this service" (Flannery 2013: 199).

Not content with Tbilisi alone, members of the Augustine Order took steps to settle three other principalities in addition to Kakheti. Ambrosio dos Anjos sent the priest Pedro dos Santos back to Goa to receive funding for settling in other Georgian territories. In *Relação dos Jornadas*, Pedro dos Santos described how the priest, who began his five-month journey, first arrived in Mtskheta where the Georgian Patriarch had been staying. Here the Georgian Patriarch Zachariah assured him that if Teimuraz did not keep word, he would personally help. The Augustinian priest who came from Mtskheta to Yerevan and from there to Nakhchivan met with the Dominican priest Augustin Bazhenk, who was elected Catholic bishop in Nakhchivan, and the bishop took him to a monastery in Ordubad. Attention needs to be drawn to the fact that Pedro dos Santos, who arrived from Tabriz after hearing about the visit of Shah Abbas I, and, to avoid meeting with the Shah, turned his way to Kashan (Flannery 2013: 175). According to the priest's notes, on the way to Kashan, he met the Dutch envoy, who informed him that Robert Shirley had been poisoned and killed by Shah Abbas I. Pedro dos Santos passed through Isfahan, Shiraz and Lar and finally arrived Goa in 1628. Here a new delegation led by Antonio de Moraes, Sebastiano de Jesus, Antonio de San Vicente and Antonio das Chagas was ready to go to Georgia. Funding for the missionaries was provided by Augustine Louis de Brito, the Governor of Estado de India. It should be noted that the Governor also presented the Georgian Patriarch with two rings, sapphire, diamonds and rubies as a gift to the Georgian King Teimuraz. Although missionaries were not allowed to trade, they were allowed to sell cinnamon in Muscat. John Flannery noted that the Georgian delegation had been assisted by members of the Augustinian Santa Monica community in Goa, who had been given watches, various furniture and writing utensils, a gilded table, and two barrels of argan and olive oils (Flannery 2013: 76). However, the delegation was led by Antonio de San Vicente and Pedro dos Santos. Another Augustinian priest died on the way as a result of a contagious disease. At the expense of the money brought, the priests settled in Gori and began building a Church in the European style.

During the period when the Augustinians sought to gain a foothold in the Georgian territories the French Kingdom managed to send the members of the missionary order of the Capuchins to the lands of the Safavids. In 1627, the ambassador of the French cardinal Richelieu Capuchin Pierre Pacific visited the Safavid palace to obtain permission for the arrival of missionaries (Khezri *et al.* 2017: 67). With the assistance of Haji Nazar, the new Khalif of Julfa, the ambassador managed to obtain permission from the Shah. In August 1629, a letter of thanks was sent from Côte d'Ivoire to Rome to protect the interests of the Catholic Church and the French Kingdom. Three months later, in November 1629, King Louis XIII of France and cardinal Richelieu granted the Armenians the right to trade between Iran and Marseilles, and this document was officially sent (Floor & Herzig 2015: 45).

However, during the reign of Shah Sefi I, the political situation in Georgia has changed. During the uprising against Teimuraz I, all the funds of the Augustinians were plundered. On the other hand, sending of a priest from two Augustinian orders to the Georgian lands by the Papacy on May 15, 1631 aroused the discontent of the Augustinian priests. Ambrosio dos Azhos noted that they represented the members of the order of Theatin at the wedding of the Prince Alexander of Imereti with the eldest daughter of Teimuraz I. However, the Greeks from Crete and Zakyntos protested to Teimuraz I and

demanded the expulsion of the missionaries. They convinced the King that Rome really intended to convert all Georgians to Catholicism (Chick & Matthee 2012: 154).

The study of the topic shows that missionary activity on the territory of Georgia failed. The actions of the missionaries aroused great discontent among the Georgian Kings and the population, as well as the missionaries faced financial difficulties. Information about the fate of the Augustinian Church and monastery in Gori can be found in the chronicles of the mid-17th century. For example, the Dominican priest Giovanni Guliani da Luca returned to Rome, the Polish commander Stanislaus Konieplauski arrived at the Safavid palace, and Paolo Pyromalli remained in the Augustinian monastery in Gori (Frazee 2006: 109).

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